

ON THE PREPARATION AND COMPOSITION OF THE ACID CARBONATES OF ALKALINE EARTHS AND LITHIUM

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The acid carbonates of strontium and lithium have been isolated for the first time in the solid state; lithium bicarbonate has been stabilised.

The regularities revealed by periodic classification of elements lead one to expect an order of decreasing stability of the bicarbonates of Cs, Rb, K, Na, Li, Ba, Sr, and Ca. While the bicarbonates of the first four elements are known in the solid state, those of the latter four were believed to exist only in aqueous solution. Attempts were made by Keiser and Leavitt (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 1711) to isolate the acid carbonates of calcium and barium by adding an excess of alcohol and ether to the aqueous solutions of the acid carbonates made by conducting excess CO_2 through a solution of the hydroxides; a white flocculent precipitate was thus formed which rapidly gave off CO_2 and left behind the normal carbonate. They, however, succeeded in isolating the solid compounds at a lower temperature and found them to possess the composition $\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot 1.75\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$ and $\text{BaCO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$. They did not extend their researches to other metals. Attempts were therefore made to isolate the acid carbonates of strontium and lithium.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Acid Carbonate of Strontium.—The compound was precipitated by mixing ice-cold solutions of strontium chloride and ammonium bicarbonate, the precipitate washed successively with ice-cold water saturated with CO_2 , alcohol, and ether, and dried at 0° . On heating to 120° it lost 43.46% of its weight, and the residue was found to contain 70% SrO. SrCO_3 contains 70.2% SrO. Hence the composition of the compound can be represented by the formula $\text{SrCO}_3 \cdot 1.60\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$.

The ratio $\text{CO}_2 : \text{SrO}$ determined by the method of Keiser and Mac Master (*ibid.*, p. 1715) was found, as mean of three determinations, to be 2.62.

Acid Carbonate of Lithium.—This compound was also precipitated by mixing ice-cold solutions of lithium chloride and ammonium bicarbonate, washed successively with ice-cold water saturated with CO_2 , alcohol, and ether, dried, and the ratio $\text{CO}_2 : \text{Li}_2\text{O}$ determined as above, found to be 2.65. The composition of this acid carbonate is thus represented by the formula $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.65\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$.

An alternative determination of the ratio $\text{CO}_2 : \text{Li}_2\text{O}$ in a solution of acid carbonate of lithium, obtained by passing excess CO_2 through a suspension of Li_2CO_3 in water containing a drop of phenolphthalein solution and agitating the mixture till the pink colour of phenolphthalein just began to reappear, gave the same value as above.

A stable form of lithium bicarbonate was prepared by precipitating a solution of lithium carbonate in carbonated water containing gelatine by means of absolute alcohol. This precipitate did not decompose at the ordinary temperature of the laboratory ($25\text{--}30^\circ$), while the other preparations rapidly decomposed above 0° .

This method of stabilisation is being tried with other unstable compounds.

The CO_2 fixing power of the four elements Li, Ca, Sr, and Ba are given by the formulae $\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot 1.75\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$; $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.65\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$; $\text{SrCO}_3 \cdot 1.60\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$; $\text{BaCO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$.